

An Approach to Detect Eye Diseases Using Deep Learning

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Abstract—Eye disease can cause vision impairment or blindness and early detection is crucial for effective treatment. Machine learning techniques have shown potential in detecting eye diseases by analysing digital images of the eye. These techniques can accurately classify three types of eye diseases, including Cataract, Diabetic retinopathy, and Redness. These models can be trained on large datasets of eye images and can also be used for screening in remote areas where access to eye specialists is limited. Despite the promising results, there are still some challenges in the application of machine learning for eye disease detection, such as the need for large annotated datasets and the requirement for high-quality images. Nonetheless, the integration of machine learning with traditional ophthalmologic methods can lead to improved accuracy and speed in disease detection and ultimately improve patient outcomes.

Keywords : Deep Learning, Image Data, Cataract, Redness, Diabetic Retinopathy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Eyes are essential part of human life, each and every person rely on the eyes to see and sense the world around them. One of the most vital senses is sight because it accounts for 80% of all information, we take in. By taking proper care of eyes, we will lower the risk of becoming blind and losing vision, while also keeping an eye out for any developing eye-conditions like glaucoma and cataracts. Most people experience eye issues at some point of time. Some of the eye issues are minor and simple to cure at home which will go away on their own, other major eye issues need assistance from the expert doctors. When these eye diseases are accurately diagnosed at an early stage, only then the progression of these eye diseases can be stopped. These eye diseases have a wide range of visually discernible symptoms. To accurately diagnose eye illnesses, it is required to analyse a wide range of symptoms. In this paper, our proposed model analyses and classifies eye diseases namely cataracts, crossed eyes, bulging eyes, uveitis and conjunctivitis.

When human readers write their reviews, which is usually a day or two later, the delayed findings cause missing follow-up, misunderstanding, and delayed treatment. By looking for lesions connected to the vascular anomalies brought on by the disease, clinicians can detect Eye Diseases. The objective of

this challenge is to test the limits of an automated detection method using colour fundus photography, ideally producing models with realistic clinical potential. Given the large number of eye disease patients, it is important to investigate the automatic classification of Cataract, Redness and Diabetic Retinopathy images for the diagnosis of Eye Disease.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

S Karthikeyan and colleagues [1] To classify the condition in this study, real-time fundus pictures were gathered from DIARETDB0, HRF Image Database, and STARE and categorised into twelve categories. The VGG19 Deep Learning Architecture is used to process the problem. To obtain maximum accuracy, the model was first optimised for 50 epochs, and their model predicted with 95.63% training accuracy and 92.21% validation accuracy.

Yu Wang et al [2] introduced the Random Implication picture Classifier Technique (RICT) to increase picture quality and model accuracy. In pre-processing, a median filter is used to eliminate noise and decrease loss. The approach is more exact, with an accuracy rate of 96.7 percent.

R. Bhavani et al [3] compare Central Retinal Equivalent of Vein (CRVE) and Central Retinal Equivalent of Artery (CRAE) measures for sickness prediction in this study. Preprocessing (grayscale conversion, noise reduction), vessel segmentation (feature extraction, vessel tracking), vessel classification, and disease prediction are all part of the proposed system. To achieve accuracy, a supervised feature extraction strategy, such as the median filter, is used.

Niloy Sikder et al [4] proposed a study in which the Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) dataset was handled using Digital Image Processing (DIP) and Machine Learning (ML). Because the majority of adults lose their vision, detecting this condition reduces blindness by 90% or more worldwide. An ensemble learning approach was utilised in this work to extract information from retinal pictures, yielding a 91% classification accuracy.

Zhentao Gao et al [5] predicted a four-degree classification task using data from different databases. The Inception-V3 network is employed as a diagnostic model, and its performance is compared to that of other popular CNN models. The model projected an accuracy of roughly 91.2% using the DCNN approach.

Toufique Ahmed Soomro et al. [6] provide the Deep Learning model and compare the techniques, emphasising the unique contributions of work throughout the papers and portraying the limitations and benefits of each study.

Ansh Saxena et al. [7] give a platform for medical diagnostics using images to researchers. They offered a study of classification algorithms acquired from various datasets in this paper. It displays the performance of pre-trained CNN models such as Xception, VGG16, VGG-19, ResNet-50, DenseNet-121, and DenseNet-169 in the classification report.

T. Johnlayoni et al. [8] offer a method for creating datasets with excellent precision. To retain picture quality, The input retinal picture is preprocessed to convert RGB to Grayscale, and noise is reduced using a median filter. The segmented picture is then utilised to forecast illness by calculating the CRAE and CRVE values using the SVM algorithm.

In their paper, D.Selvathi et al [9] provided a method to diagnose diseases using an algorithm and anticipate sickness using thermal images. In preprocessing, a Grey Level Co-occurrence Matrix is used to transform grey pictures to texture. The preprocessed image is sent into the algorithm, which generates an output with an accuracy of around 86.22%.

In this study, Gorana Gojic et al [10] evaluated previous work and its performance to improve its action for segmenting the vasculature and shown the high performing predictor for diagnosis purposes.

III. METHODOLOGY

- i. A deep learning model based on TensorFlow and Keras is used in the proposed system for identifying eye disorders such as diabetic retinopathy, cataract, and redness. The approach trains the deep learning model to recognise patterns and characteristics that are indicative of various eye disorders using a pre-trained model of the eye. The model aids in the detection of eye illness associated with a certain diagnosis or condition. The trained model may then be used to identify probable eye disorders and categorise new photos. To improve the accuracy of the model's predictions, the system additionally employs picture preparation techniques such as image normalisation and feature extraction. The proposed system's purpose is to increase the accuracy and efficiency of eye disease diagnosis, perhaps leading to earlier identification and improved patient outcomes. There are various types of image processing, including "image compression," "image upgrade," and "reclamation and

measurement extraction." It aids in reducing the amount of memory required to retain a complex image.

Fig 1. Overview of an eye.

Source: ResearchGate

The image can be stolen. The photographs may be discarded due to issues with the digitizing process and other factors. Image enhancement techniques can be used to fix a neglected image.

Background working:

- A. Data Collection
- B. Eye Detection
- C. CNN Classifier

A. Data Collection:

In this system, pre-trained Keras models are used to detect various eye disorders and their associated problems. These models employ a Convolutional Neural Network architecture and are designated ".h5" (model.h5) to indicate that they have been pre-trained. To identify eye problems, we employ pre-trained models created with the Convolutional Neural Network.

B. Eye Detection:

This approach use pre-trained Keras models to identify various eye diseases and associated complications. These models have already been trained and use a Convolutional Neural Network architecture. They are labelled with ".h5" (model.h5). To detect eye abnormalities, we use pre-trained models created with the Convolutional Neural Network.

Fig 2. Overview of eye detection.

C. CNN Classifier:

This is used to forecast eye illness. Machine learning algorithms are used to identify disease in order to check the news presented. There are several classifiers available to help you locate the illness. The classifier's accuracy is determined on how it was taught. Classifiers should be expected to be very accurate.

Fig 3. Architecture of Convolutional Neural Networks.

Source: ResearchGate

CNNs (convolutional neural networks) are a machine-learning method that is used to generate Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) that evaluate two-dimensional input. CNNs qualify as deep neural networks since they have various techniques for merging picture data in a network. Convolution is the cornerstone of CNN algorithms. It consists of convolution operations, activation layers, pooling layers, and flattening layers.

i. CNN Architecture:

A CNN is a feed-forward network with layers that use convolutional, pooling, flattening, and fully connected activation functions.

ii. Convolutional Layer:

This is the foundation of CNN. The convolution method is used in mathematics for integrating two functions. In CNN models, the input image is first converted into a matrix. The input matrix is run through a convolution filter, which conducts element-wise multiplication and saves the results. A visualisation of features is created as a consequence. It is common practise to create 2-dimensional feature maps from monochrome photos using the 3 3 filter. When the input picture appears as a 3D matrix, convolutions may be carried out in three dimensions. Many detectors of features are used in conjunction with a matrix of inputs to create a layer of mappings of features, which are then combined to create the convolutional layer.

iii. Pooling Layer:

Convolutional layers are followed by pooling layers. Max-pooling layers are used as pooling layers in all four models. The most intense values for pixel intensity from the image window now covered by the kernel are selected by the max-pooling layer, which has a size of 2. Max-pooling is used to reduce the dimensionality and complexity of sample images. There are two ways to use pooling layers: universal pools and overlapping pooling. The models presented here use the max-

pooling plan to facilitate the identification of significant visual characteristics.

iv. Flattening Layer and Fully Connected Layers:

The input picture is passed to the flattened layer after going across the pooling and convolutional layers. This layer reduces processing complexity even more by flattening the input picture into a column. The thick layer/fully connected layer is then sent this. Each node in the starting layer links to each component in the second layer, which is divided into several tiers.

IV. RESULT

Machine learning and deep learning approaches have been shown to be quite successful in diagnosing different eye illnesses. Convolutional neural network (CNN) models have demonstrated good accuracy rates in predicting eye illnesses such as cataracts, redness, and diabetic retinopathy. Early detection of certain eye illnesses can lead to more effective therapies and improved patient outcomes. These models, however, are not without flaws, and there is still opportunity for growth in terms of accuracy and performance. Overall, the creation and use of these models holds considerable potential for future advancements in the detection and treatment of eye illnesses.

Fig 4. Screenshot of cataract detected eye

V. CONCLUSION

Using pictures of the human eye and the CNN approach, we forecasted the features of the retinal eye by forecasting disorders in the human body. As a result, by supplying input in the form of an eye image, the trained model predicted whether the individual was affected or not, and it then used pre-processing techniques to give us with the output. The disorders are divided into three categories: diabetic retinopathy, cataracts, and redness. The input image will be examined to see if it contains the eye image, and then categorised into one of these disorders, yielding the result.

VI. REFERENCES

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